

CYTOGENETIC FEATURES OF CARCINOGENESIS

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At present, primary plurality of tumors refers to the presence of several independent malignant or benign neoplasms occurring synchronously or metachronously in one person. Primary multiple malignancies (MPML) can develop in a single organ, in paired organs or organs of the same system, as well as in organs and systems that are not functionally related to each other. Most frequently PMZN are observed in one organ and in the organs of different systems unlike the lesions of paired organs and organs of one system PMZN are extremely complex n poorly studied problem of oncology Their number is increasing with the growth of overall cancer morbidity, increasing life expectancy after curing patients with malignant tumors Probability of primary multiple malignancies in patients who have already had a cancer disease, 6 times higher than in people who the aim of: the present study was to investigate cytogenetic features of carcinogenesis in primary multiple malignancies.

Material and methods of the study: the study involved patients treated at RSNPMCRC in 2012-2014. To compare cytogenetic features of patients with PMZN and metastatic tumors we studied karyotypic changes in vitro according to the generally accepted principles.

Results of the study and their discussion: it is known that chromosomal instability can cause DNA displacement outside of tumor cell nuclei. This, in turn, can lead to the development of chronic intracellular inflammatory response and, thus, allow to expand the area of tumor growth.

Analysis of information on oncology patients in the RSNPMCRC from 2012 to 2014 showed that the incidence of PMZN was 0.35% of the total number of oncopathologies. For comparative characterization of cytogenetic features of patients with PMZN and with metastatic tumors we studied the characteristics of karyotypic changes in vitro.

Cytogenetic studies performed in patients with PMZN did not reveal specific chromosomal abnormalities, but chromosomal instability in the form of chromosome fragmentation and the presence of heptae was detected. Patients with metastatic tumors were also found to have no specific chromosomal abnormalities, and

chromosomal instability was in the form of small fragments and micronuclei. When studying kinetic changes in tumor cells of patients with PMZN we observed high expression of the proliferation marker Ki-67.

Cytogenetic studies to detect chromosomal instability and the presence of specific marker chromosomes reveal a symptom complex of hereditary syndromes manifested both hetero- and homozygous. The initiation of metastatic processes, usually leads to fatal outcomes in 90% of cases. Chromosomal instability leads to the generation of a multitude of genetically diverse tumor cells, and the evolutionary principle of selection determines the survival of cells that possess the properties of proliferation and formation of distant foci of tumor growth.

Human cells have evolved a molecular defense mechanism to fight this type of viral lesion by activating the cGAS-STING system, a chain of anti-inflammatory antiviral programs.

Cells characterized by chromosomal instability show increased cytosolic DNA content along with signs of chronic activation of antiviral cGAS-STING proteins.

At the same time, a decrease in cGAS-STING levels reduced the severity of the inflammatory response and limited the metastatic potential of other aggressive tumor cells. In tumor cells, inhibition of lethal elements of cGAS-STING response occurs along with activation of other parts of the indicated system, which allows to realize the goals of mobilization and expansion of tumor growth zones within the body. The observed phenomena allow us to compare the principle of tumor cell action with the response of certain immune cell types, which are usually activated by infectious agents. At the same time, tumor cell functioning is characterized by a rapid transition to an infectious response program or a scenario of pathophysiological reactions under conditions of traumatic injuries in the organism.

Thus, we can assume that cancer cells are involved in modeling some form of lethal immune mimicry.

Conclusion: our studies allow us to conclude that chromosomal instability leads to metastasis by maintaining an autonomous tumor cell response to cytosolic DNA. Also, chromosomal instability can cause DNA to move outside the tumor cell nuclei. This, in turn, can lead to the development of a chronic intracellular inflammatory response and thereby allow the spread of tumor growth to expand.

The results we obtained are of great interest, as PMZN are an excellent model of multifactorial susceptibility to cancer. The study of ASGM allows us to deepen scientific understanding of the mechanisms of carcinogenesis, develop approaches to improve prevention, diagnosis and treatment of malignant tumors. The study of gene profile of different tumors creates prerequisites for the development of not only general principles of targeted therapy for a particular type of neoplasms, but also their therapeutic individualization.

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